

Synthesis, spectral characterization and antimicrobial studies of novel acyl hydrazones of *p*-acetoxybenzaldehyde

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Abstract : Novel acyl hydrazones derived from *p*-acetoxybenzaldehyde and various acid hydrazides have been synthesized. Synthetic procedure is simple and convenient and affords good yield. Elemental analysis and spectral results of the products are also reported.

Keywords : Acyl hydrazones, *p*-acetoxybenzaldehyde, acid hydrazides, elemental analysis, IR, NMR.

Introduction

Hydrazone of acyl and aroyl compounds have an imine (C=N) group and an additional donor site like C=O. Due to these donor sites these compounds are more flexible, versatile and good chelating agents to transition metals.

N-Acyhydrazones have been widely used in organic¹⁻³ and analytical²⁻⁴ chemistry, mainly as ligands for coordination to metals^{5,6}. Hydrazone derivatives are reported to possess a wide spectrum of biological activities like antimicrobial⁷, antitubercular⁸, anticonvulsant⁹ and anti-inflammatory¹⁰ activities.

As far as we know not much study has been done on compounds containing both acyl hydrazone and acetoxy groups. We could not find any related studies on such acyl hydrazones. Thus we have designed and synthesized some novel acyl hydrazones with acetoxybenzaldehyde and various acid hydrazides. These hydrazones show appreciable antimicrobial activity.

Results and discussion

The hydrazones were obtained as crystalline compounds in good yield. The characteristic data for the compounds **a** and **b** are given below. All the physical and spectroscopic data were in accordance with the structure.

(a) 4-[(2-Benzoylhydrazinylidene)methyl]phenyl acetate :

Colorless crystals (from methanol), yield 75%, 2.2 g, m.p. 175–177 °C; FTIR (KBr) (ν cm⁻¹) : 3208 (NH),

3058 (aromatic CH), 1763 (ester C=O), 1650 (C=O), 1606 (C=N); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : 11.9 (1H, s, D₂O exchangeable), 8.49 (1H, s), 7.93 (2H, d, *J*_{HH} 7.2 Hz), 7.79 (2H, d, *J*_{HH} 8.4 Hz), 7.52–7.63 (3H, m), 7.24 (1H, d, *J*_{HH} 8.4 Hz), 2.3 (3H, s); Anal. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₄N₂O₃ : C, 68.0; H, 5.0; N, 9.9%. Found : C, 68.1; H, 5.1; N, 9.9%; *m/z* 282.29

(b) 4-[[2-(Pyridin-3-ylcarbonyl)hydrazinylidene]methyl]phenyl acetate :

Colorless crystals (from methanol), yield 73%, 2.0 g, m.p. 166–168 °C; FTIR (KBr) (ν cm⁻¹) : 3225 (NH), 3071 (aromatic CH), 1759 (ester C=O), 1656 (C=O), 1604 (C=N); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : 12.0 (1H, s, D₂O exchangeable), 9.06 (1H, s), 8.75 (1H, d, *J*_{HH} 4.4 Hz), 8.45 (1H, s), 8.25 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 7.79 (2H, d, *J*_{HH} 8.8 Hz), 7.55–7.58 (1H, dd, *J*_{HH} 4.4 Hz, 8.0 Hz), 7.23 (1H, d, *J*_{HH} 8.8 Hz), 2.28 (3H, s); Anal. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₂N₂O₄ : C, 63.6; H, 4.6; N, 14.7%. Found : C, 63.9; H, 4.4; N, 14.8%; *m/z* 283.28.

Spectral data :

IR spectra of hydrazones showed characteristic C=N band of strong intensity around 1610 cm⁻¹ and NH band of medium intensity around 3200 cm⁻¹¹¹. All the compounds showed strong ester C=O band around 1760 cm⁻¹. The absence of aldehydic C=O band and NH₂ band proved the formation of acyl hydrazones.

The azomethine proton peak, for compounds appeared as singlet around 8.5 ppm and hydrazone NH proton around 12 ppm. The signals of the protons of CH₃ of

acetoxy group, appeared as a singlet at 2.3 ppm. Peaks around 12 ppm disappeared in D₂O exchange spectra, confirming the assignment. The signals for phenyl protons of the compounds appeared between 7 and 8 ppm, whereas in compound **b** pyridyl proton resonance signals appeared between 8 and 9 ppm.

Biological studies :

We have evaluated the new ligands for *in vitro* antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus subtilis* and *in vitro* antifungal activity against *Candida albicans*. Double strength nutrient broth-I.P. and Sabouraud dextrose broth-I.P. were employed for bacterial and fungal growth respectively¹². Standard serial dilution method was used to determine Minimum Inhibitory Concentrations (MIC) and shown in Table 1. The *in vitro* activity was appreciable against the tested strains. The MIC of standard drugs for antibacterial activity (Tetracycline and Chloramphenicol) and antifungal activity (Fluconazole) were found to be < 3.12 µg/ml¹².

Table 1. The MIC (in µg/ml) of *in vitro* antimicrobial activity of the hydrazones

Compd.	Antibacterial activity		Antifungal <i>C. albicans</i>
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	
a	12.5	25	12.5
b	12.5	25	12.5

Experimental

All chemicals used in our present study were of analytical grade, procured from Sigma-Aldrich and used without any purification. TLC was run on silica (60 F₂₅₄ coated aluminum sheets) using 1 : 1 ethyl acetate and petroleum ether as mobile phase and visualized in UV light to check completion of reaction. IR spectrum was recorded using FT-IR Perkin-Elmer spectrometer. ¹H NMR spectrum was obtained using Bruker NMR instrument 400 MHz in DMSO-*d*₆ and are expressed as ppm with respect to TMS. Elemental analysis was done using Elementar Vario EL III system.

Acyl hydrazones of *p*-acetoxybenzaldehyde were synthesized according to a general method^{13,14}. The title compounds were prepared by the synthetic pathway which is presented in Scheme 1.

p-Acetoxybenzaldehyde (1.6 g, 0.01 mol) and the respective acid hydrazides (0.01 mol) [nicotinic hydrazide

Fig. 1

(1.4 g) and benzoic hydrazide (1.4 g) respectively] were mixed separately in methanol. The mixture was refluxed for 3 h. TLC was run to ensure the completion of reaction. Colorless crystals were obtained from the reaction mixture on standing. The products were filtered and recrystallised from methanol.

Conclusion

We have synthesized hydrazones and evaluated their antimicrobial activity. The sXRD structure of compound **b** is previously reported¹³. These compounds can behave as successful ligands. They can further be complexed with metal ions and their biological activity studied.

Acknowledgement

Authors like to thank Centre for Research, Christ University, Bangalore, India for the financial support, SIF, IISc, Bangalore, India for NMR data and Department of Chemistry, Bangalore University, India for elemental analysis of the compounds.

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